

Rotman Lens Development at the Army Research Lab

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Abstract—An electronic scanning antenna (ESA) that uses a beamformer for scanning the beam has the advantage of being able to form multiple beams for multimode, shared-aperture applications. This scanning approach is achieved at a reduced parts count for the antenna subassembly and therefore at a lower cost than approaches utilizing phase-shifting elements for controlling the beam. This paper discusses our efforts to realize such a beamformer using Rotman lens geometry and details some of the technologies we investigated as well as some engineering tradeoffs encountered.

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1. INTRODUCTION

This paper^{1,2} will discuss work done by (and for) the Army Research Lab in its development of Rotman Lens beamformers over the last ten years. The complex task of such development from early prototypes at K_u band to our present design at K_a band will be described including the technical tradeoffs. We have investigated both photo etched and cavity versions of these lenses. Much of the work was prompted in an effort to realize an efficient beamformer that would support multiple applications utilizing a common aperture.

One successful version was a cavity Rotman lens that served as the azimuthal beamformer for our Electrically Scanned Antenna (ESA) - developed to demonstrate that the lens would support multiple applications at the K_a band.

This lens has a 3° beamwidth and was modified from an earlier version to reduce the cost impact of tight manufacturing tolerances. A further upgrade integrated 34 phase compensated output ports. The attractive feature of the Rotman lens was its wide bandwidth of operation (36 to 40 GHz) and its multi-beam capability. Our particular lens had up to 18 input ports that were activated with an $M \times N$ beam switching network.

While this lens was successfully tested, its machining costs made it impractical from a mass production standpoint. The same design is now realized as a plastic version which could be fabricated from a mold. The plastic is then coated with a conductive coating. This is a less expensive (and lighter) lens that is functionally equivalent to the more costly version. Results will be presented and the tradeoffs outlined.

In addition to the cavity lenses, we have been active in our investigation of photo etched lenses because of their relatively low cost. However, the higher insertion loss (as compared to the cavity version) has always been a concern.

We have investigated a possible solution to this problem by considering a “surface wave” Rotman lens that could reduce conduction loss by a factor or two. Early versions of such a lens have been fabricated and measured.

Figure 1 – Rotman Lens: shaded areas show signal paths

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² IEEEAC paper #1066, Version 4, Updated Nov, 1 2005

2. ROTMAN LENS

The key to achieving a low-cost, compact, multibeam antenna is through the use of a Rotman lens that provides appropriate phasing to each element of the antenna array. One design we fabricated has 19 beam ports (on the left of Figure 1) that couple the signal into the broad parallel-plate region of the lens. The lens' geometry is chosen so that each beam port, by virtue of its position, produces the desired array phasing for its associated beam angle at the output ports. The direction the beam radiating from the antenna can therefore be controlled by selection of an appropriate beam port. Additionally, the amplitudes at the outputs are somewhat greater in the center adding sidelobe suppression.

Figure 2 – Georgia Tech Rotman lens.

The Rotman lens differs from that of other lenses in that it has three perfect focal points on the beam feed, with the other sources approximated on a circular focal arc. In other words, when a source is turned on at one of these foci, a linear phase taper appears across the linear array of output ports. The small phase errors at the intermediate positions do not significantly degrade antenna performance. The Rotman lens is inherently a wide-bandwidth device, because the path lengths to the output ports correspond to a true time delay, rather than just providing the desired phase. Therefore, the correct phasing is achieved independently of frequency. The medium used for this lens is waveguide with the E-field oriented parallel to the broad walls of the lens to reduce reflections at the input and output ports. In this orientation, the wavelength of the signal traveling thorough the lens is a function of the wall spacing. The corresponding variation of the velocity of propagation of the signal in the lens causes a shift in the beam angle with

frequency for angles off broadside. Using an electric field oriented perpendicular to the broad walls of the lens could eliminate this effect, but over the limited frequency range used here, the beam shift is small, about +/- 4%.

Some of the preliminary work that was used to develop our cavity Rotman lens was done by Georgia Tech. Their prototype is shown in Figure 2. This assembly consisted of a beam-port manifold mounted on top, connected to the Rotman lens by 19 U-shaped waveguides, which provided the desired outputs spacing to feed a 34-element sectoral horn. This arrangement makes a compact package for scanning a beam horizontally.

In the application addressed here, vertical scanning capability was needed as well. To add that capability, the sectoral horn was replaced with a patch array so as not to preclude scanning in elevation. This additional degree of scanning freedom remains a challenging issue with MEMs and ferroelectric phase shifters being two of the leading candidates for elevation scanning.

For our radar needs, we use separate transmit and receive arrays requiring separate lenses. Other factors considered in adapting the Georgia Tech design to the MFRF requirements were to reduce the size and weight while maintaining ease of manufacture. In addition, replacing Magic Ts with E-plane Ts and eliminating aperture tapering attenuators that are in the Georgia Tech design of Figure 2 simplified the design. Finally, careful reduction in manufacturing tolerances improved manufacturability with minimal impact on performance.

3. DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS

As mentioned, the original Georgia Tech Rotman used magic Ts in the implementation. The lens port spacing is larger than one half wavelength and to avoid multi-moding at that point, two apertures were used for each port, combined with a T junction. The fabrication of this junction was considerably simplified by using E-plane Ts saving on the cost of machining the waveguide ports for the terminations and the cost of 53 terminations. The split ports of an E-plane T, Figure 3, are not matches, with an S_{22} and S_{33} of about 6 dB – usually a serious mismatch. However, as used in the Rotman lens, the split ports are always fed with similar amplitudes and phases. The phase difference is

Figure 3 – E-plane Ts.

Figure 4 – Mismatch due to folded-T junctions.

greatest at an end array port when fed from an end beam port, estimated to be 58 Degrees. Figure 4 shows the mismatch as a function of this phase difference. It shows how the mismatch increases from 0 dB at the center of scan to about 6 dB for the edge array ports at the scan extremes. The consequence of the mismatch would be to reflect signal back into the lens, which could increase the sidelobe level at the scan extremes. This degradation was expected to be minimal.

The Georgia Tech version used a Taylor distribution applied to the array ports in the prototype design to reduce sidelobes, adding an attenuator in line with each port. The attenuators vary in phase shift requiring compensation in the waveguide interconnect path lengths. This cost and the cost of the attenuators themselves were saved by eliminating the attenuators. The resulting aperture distribution is nearly uniform, and a corresponding increase in the first sidelobes to about 13 dB would be expected.

The parameters carrying the greatest importance in the fabrication of the Rotman lens were cost, manufacturability, and electrical performance. Other parameters that impacted the configuration were overall size, port mating constraints, and dimensional stability (with temperature and loading.) In the case of the lens, cost and manufacturability are strongly tied. Tradeoffs between these parameters led to material selection, geometric design details (e.g., minimizing I/O waveguide lengths), tolerance specifications, limits on the minimum feature sizes, and exclusion/modification of certain electrical design features. As an example of the last point, the original design contained matched T-junctions at the waveguide-to-cavity transitions; however, the electrical performance gained by incorporating these features was not sufficient to justify the large increase in fabrication cost, and the design was modified to exclude them.

The lens was fabricated from rectangular blocks in symmetric halves as shown in Figure 5 with absorber installed. This fabrication process splits the waveguides in the center of the broad wall, where the current is at a minimum, and also reduces the vertical cutting depth for the dimensionally sensitive features. The thickness of the lens was made substantially greater than the waveguide height (7X) for structural rigidity (bending stiffness is increased by nearly 300X.) The penalty is increased mass. However, pocketing the non-lens side of the blocks reduced the weight. For fabrication tolerances, it was determined that the critical side-to-side dimensions should be held to $\pm 0.003''$, but that the tolerance for the depth should be limited to $\pm 0.005''$. Of particular concern was the flatness and alignment of the mating surfaces of the two halves. To address the alignment, pins were incorporated; and to ensure contact of mating surfaces, fourteen $\frac{1}{4} - 20$ bolts were used – together producing a nominal contact pressure of 250 psi. The material chosen was aluminum (alloy 6061-T6.) This material is easy to machine, light, corrosion resistant, and not costly. To reduce out-of-plane warping, the use of other aluminum alloys and adding an annealing stop to the fabrication process after the primary machining run were considered (due to residual stress), but were found to be unnecessary.

Figure 5 – Rotman lens - one half shown, with absorber.

4. MEASURED DATA

Both the Georgia Tech and the modified Rotman were tested in the Anechoic Chamber at the Army Research Lab. The system was operated in a receive mode and beam scanning in azimuth was measured to be greater than ± 22 Degrees. The radiation pattern at 38 GHz of a center beam port for the Georgia Tech version is given in Figure 6 while the radiation pattern for the modified ARL version is given in Figure 7. The difference in gain between the two versions is primarily due to the horn on the output of the lens narrowing the beam in elevation compared to the ARL version with open-end waveguide outputs. A composite of

patterns for each beam-port excited is given in Figure 8. The variation in gain with scan angle is presumed to be due to reflections within the lens.

Figure 6 – Georgia Tech Rotman lens.

Figure 7 – ARL Rotman lens

Figure 8 – ARL Rotman lens composite patterns.

5. OTHER ROTMAN IMPLEMENTATIONS

Printing the lens structure on a dielectric substrate reduces the overall size of the lens. This miniaturization in the size may allow for stacking multiple lenses at the output ports of the current design to allow for elevation scanning. Initial designs of these lenses were carried out at the K_u -band to minimize cost for the prototype design.

Two different approaches for the design of the dielectric loaded lens are discussed in the following sections. The first approach is a microstrip lens design, where the feeds and delay lines are printed on a dielectric with a conductor plate in the back. The second approach launches surface waves in a thicker dielectric medium where the conductor plate in the back is removed.

Figure 9 – Microstrip Rotman lens.

The objective of the development is to miniaturize the two cavity Rotman lenses used in the prototype by dielectric loading. The Rotman lens is a true time delay structure, where the input (beam) port locations determine the scan angle. The region between the input and output ports is the parallel plate region where the fields propagate from each input port with an appropriate delay in phase to the output ports to form a beam at the desired scan angle, [4]. By using a dielectric material instead of air the overall size of the lens can be reduced by a factor of $\sqrt{\epsilon_r}$, where ϵ_r is the dielectric constant of the material. Based on Rotman geometry, a K_u -band microstrip lens was designed and built using a 20-mil thick RT5870 Duroid material, as shown in Figure 9. The lens was designed to scan over 20 degrees with 7 different beam positions. A 1x16 element patch array is connected to the output ports. The overall size of the lens is about 30 cm x 35 cm.

Figure 10 – Measured beam patterns for the Microstrip Rotman lens.

Figure 11 – Measured and ideal phase performance for the Microstrip Rotman Lens.

Antenna pattern measurements were made at different input beam positions to validate the performance of the lens. Power measurements compared to a standard horn show that the Rotman lens integrated with the 1x16 element patch

array has about 9.5 dB loss at 17 GHz. The 1x16 element patch array has a gain of 12 dBi at boresight. Measured beam patterns for this lens are given in Figure 10. Variation in gain with scan angle is shown; the degree to which this variation is due to lens effects or the radiating array has not yet been determined. Measured and ideal phase performance data for this lens are given in Figure 11. As plotted, it appears that there is an anomaly near the center of the plot. Adding 360 degrees to the measured points to the right of the step makes the trace more linear but having a different slope than predicted. This difference would be consistent with a shift in the angle of the beam. It suggests that the velocity of propagation, and, therefore the effective dielectric constant, in the lens is different than expected.

Another version of the Rotman, a dielectric lens using surface waves, was considered as shown in Figure 12. This approach eliminates any need for the ground plane at the back of the lens, and significantly reduces the use of copper for the parallel plate region in the design. This is expected to reduce the copper loss in the structure. In order to propagate surface waves efficiently, thicker dielectric substrates with higher dielectric constants are preferred. The surface wave is launched using an element structure similar to a Yagi-Uda element.

Figure 12 – Surface Wave Rotman lens.

For the surface wave Rotman, two slots, which act as the driver and the reflector, are used in the design. Simulations for the two-slot element have shown that surface waves can be launched effectively in the desired direction as observed in the S-parameter curve. The thicknesses of the Duroid layers are chosen as 10 mils for the feed layer and 100 mils for the parallel plate region, so that only TM_0 mode is excited in the structure. The lens parameters are determined so that 30° is achieved. Since a higher dielectric is used, the overall size of the design is still smaller than the microstrip design. A drawing of the launch for this lens is given in Figure 13. S-parameters (HFSS simulated) are given in Figure 14.

Figure 13 – Surface wave launchers.

Figure 14 – S-parameters for the Surface Wave Rotman.

Figure 15 – Plastic Rotman Lens

As mentioned earlier, the cavity Rotman lens was machined out of Aluminum. The same lens was machined out of a plastic material, which could have been molded, and then coated with conducting plating, Figure 15. This resulted in a significant reduction of weight (about 70%) and will reduce production costs. Measured data for this lens are given in Figure 16.

Figure 16 – Composite radiation patterns for the Plastic Rotman Lens.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Several approaches have been presented for developing an efficient beamformer using a Rotman lens. Although they are in various stages of development, many of them show promise while others have demonstrated performance. The cavity Rotman represents a mature and understood technology that is being refined to a less costly and lighter weight plastic version. A prototype K_u -band microstrip lens has been designed and built demonstrating suitable performance. In an effort to further miniaturize the design and reduce the conductor loss, the ground planes in the parallel plate region of the lens are removed by introducing a surface wave launching element and utilizing the surface wave TM_0 mode. A dielectric lens using this approach has also been designed and tested demonstrating promising performance. As efficient beamformers are critical to ESAs, it is important to develop a matrix of candidates for future use. A number of conceptual (and realized) designs were described in this paper.

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BIOGRAPHY

Dr. Steven Weiss is a senior electrical engineer with the Army Research Lab where he has worked since 1988. He has worked on a variety of military antenna systems from specialized single element radiators for fuzing applications to array antennas for Multi Function RF (MFRF) antenna systems. Dr. Weiss

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Mr. Robert K. Dahlstrom received his B.S.E.E. in 1966 from Bucknell University and his M.S.E.E. in 1967 from Carnegie Mellon University. He has worked at the Harry Diamond Laboratories, now incorporated into the Army Research Laboratory, since then as an Electronics Engineer specializing in

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